

ON THE TRANSIENT MECHANISM OF WATER-PARTICLE INDUCED LOW-ADHESION PHENOMENON

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Abstract: The phenomenon called “wet-rail” describes a sudden drop in the friction coefficient when water, iron oxides, or other fine particles mix to form a paste-like third body. Although the phenomenon is well known from railway operations, the physical relationships are not yet fully understood. The aim is to provide experimental evidence of the transient nature of the phenomenon in rolling contacts contaminated with a water-particle suspension based on optical observation of the contact. The results support the water-driven starvation mechanism triggering particle accumulation and load-carrying capacity of the transient solid film.

Keywords: Wheel/rail interface; low-adhesion phenomenon; solid particles; suspension; transient friction.

1. Introduction

The wheel-rail interface is subject to many kinds of environmental influences. Natural contaminants like water, wear particles, iron oxides, mineral particles, etc., strongly influence the rail and wheel adhesion. The early experiments by Beagley [1] have demonstrated that a small amount of water mixed with wear debris forms a lubricating paste, resulting in a transient response with a low adhesion coefficient. Over the last years, many authors have observed this trend using twin-disc or ball-on-disc setups for various mixtures of solids and water, often reaching adhesion less than 0.05, see Figure 1 [2],[3]. The decrease in adhesion is more pronounced when less water is applied. In the railway context, this action of water is called the “Wet Rail Phenomenon” and is associated with dew on the head of the rail, misty conditions and very light rain [4].

Recent studies have indicated that this transient behaviour is related to the change in the rheology of the friction layer when the water in the suspension evaporates or is displaced from the contact. First modelling attempts were made by Beagley [4], who used a model derived from parallel plate plastometry to estimate surface separation and shear strength of the water/iron oxide mixture. This pioneering work has only recently been followed up by other researchers. Buckley-Johnstone et al. [6] used the same plastometry principle together with a statistical roughness distribution to estimate the load portion carried by asperities and mixture. White et al. [7]

Figure 1 Summary of experimental reports of sudden friction drop in concentrated contacts contaminated with liquid-solid suspension.

updated the rheology parameters to estimate the occurrence of low adhesion in twin-disc testing. The updated inputs showed an adhesion drop occurring closer to 80% of the solid fraction. A phenomenological model of water-induced low adhesion (WILAC) has been proposed by Trummer et al. [8]. The parametric model describes the influence of water amount on the coefficient of adhesion for various running conditions. A coefficient of adhesion as low as 0.05 was found based on the model and a tram wheel test rig. Recently, Kvarda et al. [9] introduced a simple two-stage model capturing how small volumes of water containing suspended solid particles evolve to cause successive phases of friction drop and recovery. During Stage 1, a small meniscus reservoir sits before the contact, gradually shrinking over time, while friction stays at an intermediate level. In Stage 2, once the meniscus disappears, the solid particles concentrate within the contact, forming a “valley” of extremely low friction until the contaminant film breaks up or dries out, at this point, friction recovers. Although this approach explains many observed features (timing and severity of friction drops, length of the recovery period), it also highlights unresolved questions around how surface topography, water evaporation, particle migration, and particle shape or size distribution might further influence friction behaviour.

Although those phenomenological models provide a satisfactory estimate of processes occurring in contact with a water/solid particle suspension, they are based on the extrapolation of experimental data. These wet-rail

models treat the suspension as a bulk, homogeneous material whose shear response is dictated by a yield - stress curve measured in a conventional rheometer. It cannot by itself capture the non-monotonic, geometry- and transport-driven evolution of shear strength that governs the wet-rail low-adhesion valley. In particular, questions regarding the mechanism of contact dewatering and particle migration remain unanswered.

To address this gap, the present study unifies two complementary experimental approaches. A Mini Traction Machine (MTM) provides precise traction measurements, while a custom transparent ball-on-disc tribometer captures the contact area and third-body evolution with sub-micron resolution. This contribution aims to clarify the mechanism of the water-particle-induced low-adhesion phenomenon based on direct observation of the rolling-sliding concentrated contact.

Figure 2 Scheme of the ball-on-disc tribometers used: (a) Mini Traction Machine (MTM); (b) Optical tribometer.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Mini-Traction Machine

Two types of ball-on-disc tribometers were utilised to simulate rolling-sliding concentrated contact. A rolling-sliding ball-on-disc tribometer (Mini Traction Machine, PCS Instruments), shown schematically in Figure 2 (a), was employed to monitor how a water-particle mixture alters the coefficient of adhesion. The rig uses a 19.05 mm-diameter steel ball pressed against a 46 mm steel disc. Both shafts are driven by independent servomotors, allowing the slide-to-roll ratio (SRR) to be set with high accuracy, defined as follows:

$$SRR = \frac{v_{disc} - v_{ball}}{v_{disc} + v_{ball}} \cdot 200\%$$

Normal load and tangential (friction) load are sensed by a calibrated transducer mounted on the ball carriage. The coefficient of traction (CoT) is calculated online as the ratio of the two forces and logged at 1 Hz.

All specimens were machined from AISI 52100 bearing steel. The ball hardness was 800–920 HV and the disc 720–780 HV, with initial surface roughnesses of 0.01 μm and 0.02 μm (Ra), respectively. Although not identical to wheel and rail grades, this alloy offers chemically stable, repeatable surfaces and minimises debris generation during testing. Before each run, the ball and disc were degreased with acetone and subjected to a dry run-in until μ stabilised at ≈ 0.5 ; this procedure produced a post-run-in roughness of 0.2–0.3 μm on both bodies.

The mean rolling speed was fixed at 0.30 m s^{-1} with an SRR of 5 %. Under pure water, these parameters yield $\lambda < 0.1$, placing the contact firmly in the boundary regime. A normal load of 16 N generated a maximum Hertz. pressure of 750 MPa, typical for light-rail systems.

2.2. Optical Ball-on-Disc Tribometer

To provide direct insight into the contact, the optical tribometer, where the contact is formed between the polished AISI 52100 ball and the Sapphire disc, was used; see Figure 2 (b). The ball and disc drives allow precise control of SRR. A load is applied through a disc with a dead weight at the required contact pressure. A torque transducer on the ball spindle supplies the friction signal, which is synchronised with the video stream during post-processing. The mean rolling speed of 0.30 m s^{-1} and an SRR of 5 % were the same as for the MTM test. A larger load of 40 N, resulting in a Hertzian pressure of 1 GPa, was used. Due to the very low roughness and easy disc scratching, no run-in under dry conditions was carried out.

The optical setup includes an industrial microscope with a lens. The contact is illuminated with a high-intensity LED source and captured with a high-speed camera at 1,000 fps. The tribometer was developed at the Brno University of Technology for lubricant film-thickness measurement using Thin-film colorimetric interferometry [10] or Light-induced fluorescence imaging [11]. In the current study, lubricant film thickness is not measured because of technical limits and a limited light transmission through the dense suspension.

2.3. Water-particle suspension

Water-particle suspension was mixed using distilled water and 5 μm Talc flakes, as in previous studies [2],[9],[12]. Talc, a hydrous magnesium silicate mineral, is not a typical rail contaminant; however, because of a layered structure with weak van der Waals forces, it exhibits a low friction with a significant drop in the rolling-sliding contact.

Initial solid fractions of 0 to 50 wt% were examined using MTM. In this case, 50 μl of suspension was applied to the contact just after the running-in, resulting in the initial drop in CoT. In the case of the optical tribometer, the solid fraction was fixed to 5 wt% . Because the ball sits below the disc, 100 μl of suspension was deposited as 20 equal droplets around the disc circumference before start-up; this arrangement ensures continuous entrainment but does not allow for observing the primary CoT drop seen on the MTM.

3. Results

3.1. Mini-Traction Machine

Figure 3 (a) illustrates the typical complete drying cycle for a 5 wt % Talc suspension. Four distinct regimes are evident, matching earlier wet-rail studies [2],[9],[12]. After a dry run-in, water-talc mix is injected at $t=0$. Within the first second, the CoT drops from 0.52 to 0.30 and stabilises – region I – signalling boundary lubrication controlled by asperity contacts. After several dozen seconds, CoT falls precipitously to 0.08, defining region II. The deepest low-adhesion valley (region III) lasts several seconds with a minimum CoT of 0.037. A slight rebound to the lowest value confirms the tertiary drop, after which CoT slowly recovers to dry friction (region IV). The slight rebound between CoT 0.2 and 0.3 in region IV is typical for the MTM. Coefficient-of-variation across repeats is 2.8%, demonstrating excellent run-to-run stability.

Figure 3 MTM results: (a) CoT vs. time (5% Talc, 0.3 m/s, 750 MPa, SRR 0.05, 50 μ l); (b) Relative duration of the phases vs. Initial Talc concentration.

The test with 5 wt % suspension was used because of a representative behaviour in all four phases. Initial talc concentration changes the duration and proportion of the phases. All the tests made for the initial concentration ranging from 0 to 50 wt % are summarised in Figure 3 (b). The plot shows which regions dominate during the drying process. It is evident that for the concentration above 0.12, the first phase disappears and the contact operates in the low-friction region for a longer time. On the other hand, above 20 wt %, recovery region IV starts to dominate against the lowest CoT region III. The proportional duration of the recovery area linearly increases with the increase in the initial concentration.

The time from the application of the suspension to the restoration of traction is plotted in Figure 4 (a). This time depends on the amount of water at the beginning of the experiment. The figure detected a linear relationship between the amount of water applied and the experiment's total duration. The different initial suspension concentrations primarily influenced the reduction of the water volume in the suspension.

The duration of the very low CoT area significantly depends on the particle mass in the applied suspension (Fig. 4 b). As the concentration increased, the duration of the very low traction area also increased. This trend was the same for all tested suspensions. The turning point occurred when a suspension with an initial concentration higher than the critical concentration was applied. In such cases, the duration of very low traction no longer increased but instead began to shorten. This was due to the small amount of water in the suspension, leading to rapid drying and restoration of traction.

Figure 4 MTM results: (a) Time to recovery vs. initial water amount (various concentration and amount, 0.3 m/s, 750 MPa, SRR 0.05, 50 μ l); (b) Influence of talc volume in applied suspension on the duration of very low traction area.

3.2. Optical Tribometer

Figure 5 illustrates the typical optical representation of the running contact area between the disc and ball, supplemented with its schematic representation. In the middle of the image, covering app. 2x2 mm, the Hertzian circular contact area is visible, which is bordered by weak interference fringes that form as a result of light interference on a thin layer of water between a steel ball and a Sapphire disk. Each colour in this area corresponds to lubricant film thickness and can be evaluated based on a calibration, although this approach has not been applied in this study. Under the chosen testing conditions, the typical central water film thickness is below 15 nm [13].

The first image also clearly shows a so-called meniscus boundary between air and liquid, representing a kind of suspension reservoir around the contact, formed by capillary effects. Solid particles are apparent as dark shadings in the pictures since they are too small to distinguish. It can be seen that particles tend to flow around the contact instead of going through the contact as they are approaching the converging gap. In this stage, solid particle concentration and therewith viscosity vary around and within the contact, introducing additional complexity. Due to the narrow gap between the surfaces, it is difficult for the solid particles to go through the contact. Particles form a dry film on the contact bodies outside the flooded area.

The images from the various phases of the CoF evolution for the typical 5 wt% concentration are summarised in Figure 6 (a). The photos are attributed to the phases described on data from the MTM test (Figure 6 (b)). Optical tribometer provides similar trends in CoT. Nevertheless, individual events in the CoT data are more easily distinguishable for the MTM steel-steel configuration. Under the fully-flooded part (Point 1), solid particles travel around the contact and asperity contact occurs because of low hydrodynamic action. During the water evaporation (Point 2), a liquid film meniscus approaches the Hertzian contact, drawing solid particles into it. This increases lubricating film thickness and a drop in friction (Point 3.). Later in time, the particles are expelled from the contact, corresponding to an increase in friction to a stable “dry” level (Point 4.).

This observation indicates that the phenomenon is connected with the transient increase in solid film thickness due to their attraction to the water meniscus and subsequent water evaporation.

Figure 5 Optical tribometer, typical optical representation of the running contact area between the disc and ball and its schematic representation.

Figure 6 (a) Images captured at given moments (1.-4.) using optical tribometer; (b) corresponding test on MTM with the illustration of the contact behaviour.

4. Discussion

The combined MTM–optical dataset corroborates the four-phase narrative hinted at in earlier twin-disc studies but never visualised in situ. Immediately after suspension injection, the contact behaves like a mildly starved EHL system; asperity interactions dominate, and the CoA stabilises around 0.25. A concave meniscus advances toward the Hertzian half-width as the external reservoir shrinks. Capillary forces at this curved interface funnel talc particles into the inlet, where they compact into a quasi-solid film. Optical interferometry reveals that the local film thickness surges roughly from 50 nm to 300 nm within 1–3 s, coinciding with the second drop in CoT. The ensuing low-adhesion valley persists until evaporation reduces the capillary suction below the yield stress of the packed layer; at that point, shearing expels the particles, and metal-to-metal contact re-establishes mixed lubrication.

These observations strongly support the hypotheses that water-driven starvation is the trigger for particle accumulation and that the load-carrying capacity of the transient solid film is limited, making the phenomenon inherently temporal. Quantitatively, the residence time of the valley scales nearly linearly with the cube of the initial suspension volume, indicating a diffusion-limited drying process. It is evident that the secondary drop is initiated precisely when the advancing meniscus reaches the Hertzian half-width, not when the global water fraction crosses an arbitrary threshold. This geometric trigger explains why seemingly identical bulk water contents can yield radically different adhesion outcomes on tracks with varying diameters of wheel or railhead roughness. The shear strength of the packed particle layer decreases during its formation, even though bulk rheometry predicts a monotonic rise with solids fraction. Such softening is attributed to liquid entrapment between force chains that should be investigated in more detail.

Comparison with the two-stage model of Kvarda et al. [9] shows encouraging agreement: the experimentally fitted ratio of reservoir depletion rate (k_1) to film compaction rate (k_2) lies between 2 and 4 across all Talc concentrations, matching the range used for successful CoT prediction. However, the model currently treats concentration and film thickness as lumped parameters; incorporating the image-derived meniscus position should improve its temporal fidelity. Finally, we note that the harder AISI 52100 surfaces used here likely overpredict the valley duration relative to R260 steel because of reduced third-body generation—an aspect to be addressed in future wheel-on-rail rigs.

The study employed talc as a chemically inert particle. The pronounced valley depth observed with talc can be rationalised by its mineralogy. Talc platelets possess a basal (001) plane held together only by weak van der Waals forces; when they orient parallel to the sliding direction, they behave as solid lubricants with an intrinsic shear strength below 5 MPa—three orders of magnitude lower than that of oxides. In addition, the platelet aspect ratio (~10:1) fosters rapid formation of a contiguous, highly anisotropic layer once capillary suction draws the

particles into the inlet. All the aspects differ from the real rail debris, which comprises oxides, silica and organic residues with different surface energies. However, the CoT trends indicate that the basic mechanism of the dewatering process will be similar, regardless of the lowest CoT level. Despite this, the relevance of the results needs to be verified with another type of solid particle.

Therefore, Future experiments will employ more realistic particles and integrate real wheel-rail specimens under twin-disc kinematics. On the modelling side, the optically measured meniscus position and film thickness will be used to calibrate a capillary-poro-elastic model that, when coupled to multi-body train dynamics, could predict adhesion loss on a metre-scale resolution. Finally, chemical modifiers that either suppress bed cohesion or enhance early drainage will be screened to translate the findings into tangible mitigation products.

Scaling laboratory times by vehicle speed shows that a 40 s valley at 0.30 m s^{-1} translates to a 2.4 km slippery track section at 60 km h^{-1} . Such distances exceed the length of many urban blocks, explaining why drivers often traverse an entire station-to-station segment before adhesion recovers. Interventions should therefore target the pre-valley window: sanding within the seconds of the meniscus appearing on the railhead, forced air jets on critical gradients, or hydrophilic coatings that accelerate water drainage. The exponential decay of meniscus length implies that even moderate heat input could halve the valley distance.

5. Conclusions

The study is motivated by the issue of low adhesion in wheel-rail contacts, which can cause serious problems with traction and braking in railways. This issue is frequently connected to the ‘wet-rail’ phenomenon, where the contact is naturally contaminated with water and solid particles. A significant drop in the friction coefficient can be observed at a critical particle concentration.

The work based on optical observation clearly shows what happens near the contact during the friction drop. This transient mechanism related to water evaporation shows the importance of water as a trigger for low-adhesion problems. The so-called “wet-rail” phenomenon is at the forefront of interest of rail operators and engineers since it causes significant losses due to train delays, platform overrunning, etc. Addressing this problem at the basic research level provides new insights that significantly impact the modelling and development of prediction tools and suitable mitigation techniques.

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Data availability

The data supporting the findings of this study have been deposited in the Zenodo repository ([10.5281/zenodo.17034156](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17034156)) and will be made publicly available upon publication of the final article.

References

- [1] T.M. Beagley, C. Pritchard: *Wheel/rail adhesion — the overriding influence of water*, *Wear*, 1975, 35 (2) 299–313.
- [2] R. Galas et al.: *The role of constituents contained in water-based friction modifiers for top-of-rail application*, *Tribology International*, 2018, 117 (1) 87–97.
- [3] D.V. Gutsulyak, L.J. Stanlake, H. Qi: *Twin disc evaluation of third-body materials in the wheel/rail interface*, *Tribology – Materials, Surfaces & Interfaces*, 2021, 15 (2) 115–126.
- [4] Adhesion Research Group: *Investigation into the effect of moisture on rail adhesion (T1042)*, RSSB Report, 2014, <https://www.sparkrail.org/Lists/Records/DispForm.aspx?ID=11364>
- [5] T.M. Beagley: *The Rheological Properties of Solid Rail Contaminants and their Effect on Wheel/Rail Adhesion*, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers*, 1976, 190 (1) 419–428.
- [6] L.E. Buckley-Johnstone et al.: *Assessing the impact of small amounts of water and iron oxides on adhesion in the wheel/rail interface using High Pressure Torsion testing*, *Tribology International*, 2019, 135 55–64.
- [7] B. White, R. Kempka, P. Laity, C. Holland, K. Six, G. Trummer, L. Buckley-Johnstone, and R. Lewis: *Iron Oxide and Water Paste Rheology and Its Effect on Low Adhesion in the Wheel/Rail Interface*, *Tribology Letters*, 2022, 70(1), 2022.
- [8] G. Trummer, L. E. Buckley-Johnstone, P. Voltr, A. Meierhofer, R. Lewis, and K. Six: *Wheel-rail creep force model for predicting water induced low adhesion phenomena*, *Tribology International*, 2017, 109, 409-415.
- [9] D. Kvarda, A. Meierhofer, and K. Six: *Testing and modelling of transient adhesion phenomena in rolling-sliding contacts*, *Friction*, 2024, 12(5), 1016-1027.
- [10] M. Hartl, I. Křupka, M. Liška: *Differential Colorimetry: Tool for Evaluation of Chromatic Interference Patterns*, *Optical Engineering*, 1997, 36 2384–2391.
- [11] D. Nečas et al.: *The Effect of Kinematic Conditions on Film Thickness in Compliant Lubricated Contact*, *Journal of Tribology*, 2018, 140 (5) 051501.
- [12] D. Kvarda et al.: *The effect of top-of-rail lubricant composition on adhesion and rheological behaviour*, *Engineering Science and Technology, an International Journal*, 2022, 35 1–9.
- [13] D. Kvarda et al.: *Asperity-based model for prediction of traction in water-contaminated wheel-rail contact*, *Tribology International*, 2021, 157 106900.